

Information System Analysis and Design (September 2021)

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Abstract—This scientific paper entitled “Information System Analysis and Design” is motivated to know about Information System Analysis and Design. Information systems are needed to increase effectiveness and reduce errors due to human error. The general purpose of the information system is to provide information that can assist the management decision-making process, facilitate the implementation of daily operations, and provide appropriate information for parties outside the organization, especially regarding the issue of management transparency. Information systems can be used by designing and analyzing systems. Then, add information to suit the user's needs. The purpose of using information systems is to obtain communication lines, process transaction types, convey signals to management levels as a basis for information in decision making. This journal will discuss the use of information systems in various activities based on several case studies based on several journals obtained through the *Journal of Optimization and Industrial Systems/Jurnal Optimasi dan Sistem Industri*. The conclusion obtained is, the analysis and design of information systems is very useful to facilitate human life.

Index Terms—*Analysis, Design, Effectivity, Information System, Management*

I. INTRODUCTION

Along with the times, many changes occur in various aspects of life. One of the changes that are very basic and have a significant effect on people's lives is the rapid progress of technology. As one of the basic needs of humans as social beings, of course the development of this technology has implications for the ease of carrying out activities to access accurate and reliable information.

The importance of information can also be seen through the use of information systems. Meanwhile, the definition of an information system is part of an organizational system which is a combination of users and available resources such as technology and information control media. The purpose of using information systems is to obtain communication lines, process transaction types, convey signals to management levels as a basis for information in decision making [1].

Because it has a big role in human life, knowledge about this information system is very important to know and learn. Knowledge of information systems is also relatively easy to access so that it supports anyone who wants to learn this.

Education on information systems is also available within the scope of formal education so that the younger generation will also have adequate knowledge. The background of writing this journal is to fulfil assignments in the Information System Analysis and Design course and to know the theoretical foundations of information system analysis and design.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Information system consists of two words, namely system and information. The system is a collection of various elements or elements that interact with each other to achieve certain goals. It can also mean a network of interconnected work to carry out an activity or complete a particular goal. An example of a system is a group of people, machines, things, or other types of entities. Meanwhile, information means the result of data processing that has a certain value or meaning. So, the information system can be interpreted as a system that connects the needs of daily transaction processing, operation support, management activities, and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports, both for internal and certain external parties [2].

Information systems have several functions, including improving the accessibility of existing data effectively and efficiently to users without using an information system intermediary. Improve the productivity of application systems development and maintenance, ensure the availability of quality and skills in critical use of information systems, identify the need for information systems support skills, anticipate and understand the economic consequences, determine which investments will be directed to information systems, and develop an effective planning process [3].

The information system has several components, namely [3]:

- 1) *The input component is in the form of data that enters the information system.*
- 2) *Model components are a combination of procedures, logic, and mathematical models.*
- 3) *Component output in the form of useful information for all users of the system.*
- 4) *Technology components in the form of tools in the information system to receive input, run models, store and access data, generate and transmit output, and monitor system control.*
- 5) *The power base component is a collection of interconnected data.*

6) *Control components that control disturbances to the information system.*

The characteristics of information systems are [4]:

1) *New*

It means that the information obtained is completely new and fresh for the recipient.

2) *Additional*

It means that information can be updated or add to the previously existing information.

3) *Collective*

It means information can be a correction of previous incorrect information.

4) *Confirmation*

It means information can reinforce existing information.

The general purpose of the information system is to provide information that can assist the management decision-making process, facilitate the implementation of daily operations, and provide appropriate information for parties outside the organization, especially regarding the issue of management transparency.

The static structure of the information system is described by a class diagram consisting of a collection of static elements of models, such as classes and their contents and the relationship between these classes. Various types of relationships between classes that may occur in class diagrams include [2]:

1) *Association*

It means the relationship between classes with a common meaning. Usually, this relation is equipped with multiplicity.

2) *Aggregation*

It means the description of the relationship between classes which shows that the class is part of another class.

3) *Generalization*

It means relations that show the relationship between classes with general-specific meaning.

4) *Dependencies*

It describe the dependence between classes, where a class affects other classes.

Database can be defined as a collection of data that is integrated, organized and stored in a way so that it can be retrieved easily. A database is formed from a collection of files. Files can be categorized into several types, including [2]:

1) *Master Files*

This file type is divided into a reference master file whose storage is relatively static (it rarely changes its value) and a dynamic master file that changes frequently.

2) *Transaction Files*

The use of this file type is to record data resulting from a transaction that contains a record of the date of the transaction.

3) *Report Files*

This file type contains the information to be displayed.

4) *History Files*

Contains past data that is no longer active, but needs to be saved for future purposes.

5) *Backup Files*

It is a copy of the file that is still active in the database at a certain time.

6) *Working Files*

This file type is created by a program process temporarily due to insufficient computer memory or to save memory usage during the process. This file will be deleted when the process is complete.

III. DISCUSSION

This section will discuss the review of journals published by the Industrial System Optimization Journal/Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri (JOSI).

A. *The First Journal*

The discussion of this first journal is based on the journal entitled "Perbaikan Pengelolaan Pergudangan Melalui Penerapan Sistem Informasi Pergudangan di CV. ABB" that was published in 2017 by the Industrial System Optimization Journal/Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri (JOSI).

The problems that become the focus of the researcher are warehouse data collection, part request data, spare part stock data, spare part expenditure data, and purchase order data which is still very manual. This makes employee error prone and allows for data manipulation. Another negative impact of manual warehouse management is that therefore, the research contained in this journal is carried out with the aim of establishing a web-based information system so that it can help facilitate spare part supervision because it is cheap and relatively easy to use without having to install from the client side. So, the warehouse management in CV. ABB could be better, accountable, and transparent.

There are six stages of this research methodology, namely initial observation, problem identification, literature study, data collection, system analysis and design, and conclusions and follow-up. The results obtained through this study are user requirements, analysis of current systems, design and comparative analysis between warehousing without an information system and warehousing with an information system. The required user requirements include users to minimize fraud, warehouse, finance, and admin.

Through a comparative analysis between warehousing without an information system and warehousing with an information system, several comparisons are obtained that warehousing without an information system allows for data manipulation, workshop people come to the warehouse to order spare parts, warehouse people come to finance and provide receipts for purchasing spare parts at low prices. which is much different, warehouse people usually buy goods whose stock has run out without orders from superiors, and it is difficult to control incoming and outgoing spare parts.

Meanwhile, warehousing with an information system will anticipate these things by including finance in the purchase of goods to avoid fake receipts, warehouse people are no longer allowed to provide spare part purchase receipts, users can request parts through the warehousing information system, minimizing the chance of data manipulation, warehouse people do not do their job manually, there are reports of incoming spare parts, and it is easy to control spare parts.

The conclusion obtained through this research is the

information system implemented in CV. ABB has succeeded quite effectively in overcoming problems in warehousing management and making warehousing management more accountable and transparent [5].

B. The Second Journal

The discussion of this second journal is based on the journal entitled “Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pemasaran Biduk Wisata Pulau Berbasis *Web Mobile*” that was published in 2019 by the Industrial System Optimization Journal/ Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri (JOSI). The purpose of this research is to design an online web-based marketing information system for the strategy of increasing the fisherman's business using the PHP programming language and supported by a MySQL database. It is hoped that the results of this study can increase the number of tourists who use the island as an effort to increase the economy of the Big Dipper fishermen.

There are five stages of this research methodology, namely the needs analysis stage, the database system design stage, the marketing information system design stage, the validation stage, and the implementation stage. The problem obtained through needs analysis is that there is no effective product marketing facility. This causes the island tourism transportation services from fishermen on the Pisang River to be more widely known.

So, product marketing is carried out through internet media by collecting and storing data related to island tourism in Sungai Pisang in a database designed using MySQL. Then, this database is used in the designed marketing information system. The design of this mobile web-based information system can update information about island tour packages, attractions on tourist islands, tour schedules, and tourist promos. There will also be photos showing the beauty of the tourist island [6].

C. The Third Journal

The discussion of this third journal is based on the journal entitled “Perancangan Sistem Informasi Pengendalian Kualitas pada Laboratorium Proses IV PT X” that was published in 2018 by the Industrial System Optimization Journal/ Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri (JOSI). The problem that is the focus of the researcher is the Process IV Laboratory which still uses spreadsheets as an application to support information systems. This causes a slowdown in the rate of information flow which results in a decrease in system efficiency and reliability because the work is still done manually. Then, it also opens up opportunities for various forms of fraud due to the lack of security services built into the software.

Therefore, the research contained in this journal was carried out with the aim of designing a more efficient quality control information system and supporting web-based applications at the Process Laboratory IV PT X.

The research focuses on the flow of information related to material test results from Operator 1 to the Evaluation Staff and Operator Central Control Room (CCP). Research on case studies in this journal is divided into four stages, namely preliminary studies, information systems analysis, information system design, and web-based application design.

The results obtained from the first stage, namely a preliminary study, of the spreadsheet-based information system used at the Process Laboratory IV PT X showed several weaknesses in the form of a slow information flow rate, minimal level of information security, and the potential for fraud. Through the information system using a web-based application designed by the researcher, several differences were obtained, such as increasing information security, reducing fraud involving data manipulation by other parties, eliminating the repetition of data point input repetition activities that are usually carried out by operator 1 thereby reducing the time required for processing data. carry out the entire process and minimize the potential for human error. The conclusion obtained by the researcher is that the design of an information system with a web-based application is able to increase efficiency and minimize the weaknesses of the existing information system at the Process Laboratory IV PT X at this time.

Suggestions to be noted from researchers for further research is that research can be directed at two levels. The first level is a more limited level, it is hoped that the design of an information system with web-based applications at the Process IV PT Laboratory can be developed so that it becomes a Decision Support System (DSS). The second level is a broader level, the application of information system design with web-based applications can be expanded to cover all Process Laboratories at PT. X [2].

D. The Fourth Journal

The discussion of this fourth journal is based on the journal entitled “Optimasi AHP dalam mendukung UMKM di Bangka Belitung dalam memanfaatkan E-Commerce” which was published in 2018 by the Industrial System Optimization Journal/ Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri (JOSI). The thing that is the focus of discussion in this journal is the influence of information technology in business which gives rise to a digital transaction model or e-commerce. AHP can be used by business people to evaluate their business strategies related to customer service, geographic area, using business support technology, and the amount of profit.

The methodology used is the object of research conducted in the Province of the Bangka Belitung Islands, data collection carried out by observation and literature study, research instruments using questionnaires and Expert Choice software, making analytical hierarchies, and weighting ratios of pairwise comparisons.

The conclusion obtained by the researcher is that the technological constraint factor is the most influencing factor in the use of e-commerce with a weight of 33.2% [7].

E. The Fifth Journal

The discussion of this fourth journal is based on the journal entitled “Aplikasi Penentuan Rute Distribusi LPG 3KG” which was published in 2018 by the Industrial System Optimization Journal/ Jurnal Optimasi Sistem Industri (JOSI).

The problem of discussion in this journal is to determinate routes and scheduling in which several restrictions are held such

as limiting the capacity of some vehicles. The purpose of this study was to determine the transportation route for the delivery of 3 kg LPG at PT IB Sumberdaya Development, in order to obtain optimal mileage, travel time, and transportation costs. Then, the application is designed with the hope that the 3 kg LPG delivery process runs optimally.

The research method used is primary and secondary data processing. The steps taken are to determine the distance, time, and cost based on the actual route. Next, determine the distance, time, and cost based on the proposed route. Finally, designing a program to determine the travel time and transportation costs of 3 kg LPG shipments.

The results of this study are the route and schedule for the delivery of 3 kg LPG which is designed with delivery conditions on Monday to Saturday with each of the seven routes being better than the actual route implemented by the company so far [8].

IV. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this journal is that information systems have a positive impact in various aspects of life. Information systems also increase the effectiveness of an activity and reduce errors due to human error as can occur when applying a manual system. Thus, based on several case studies discussed in this journal, several conclusions can be drawn, including:

- 1) *Information systems can make the management system in a company better, accountable, and transparent.*
- 2) *Information systems can be useful in the field of tourism by facilitating promotional activities so that information about a tourist spot is more easily accessible to many people.*
- 3) *Information systems can reduce the possibility of human error.*
- 4) *Technological constraints can affect the use of e-commerce.*
- 5) *The use of applications can help minimize travel time, mileage, and optimal transportation costs for a company.*

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